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The essential unity of law and justice is already inherent in the etymology of these words (in English “equity” and “justice”, in Latin “equity” and “court”). Justice is embodied in law, and law exists only as fair law. An unjust right is nonsense, like “dirty purity.” Legislation may be unjust, but in this case the legislation represents the arbitrariness of state power, which deprives itself of support in public legal consciousness.

Science (sociology) does not know what justice is. It can only state the pattern of human communication, which consists of maintaining a balance between giving and receiving in the process of exchanging ideas, emotions, information, material and spiritual benefits. The measure by which equivalent exchange is carried out is called equity. Injustice is a situation in which there are unfulfilled expectations and unfulfilled efforts.

Philosophy cannot be satisfied with such an explanation of justice, since its criteria and relationship with other human values - freedom, law, humanism - remain unclear. We need an essential definition of justice, without which it is difficult to understand the origin of social energy that overturns age-old dynasties, political regimes, and traditional norms. No government, no state can stand before people who thirst for justice and do not find it in legal institutions.

The formula of justice was revealed to the world by Roman jurists, who proclaimed: “To each his own!” In this formula, justice is a universal law, according to which every being has the right to count only on what corresponds to its essence. Thanks to the principle of justice, we verify the world as it is. Social

relations become stable if everyone has in life something that corresponds to his merits. What, however, is considered merit?

It is clear that the merit of a warrior will be courage, and the merit of a doctor will be caution. Virtue consists of being consistent with your essence. Since people are different due to their natural gifts, social status, professional skills, and personal culture, a fair structure of life is so that everyone can succeed in their capacity and realize the potential inherent in them. Justice, therefore, includes the demand for freedom, without which no one can become himself. Self-indifference eliminates the need for freedom and sensitivity to justice. If I have not found my place in the world and cannot call anything mine, I have nothing to claim, I am not a reason for a fair arrangement of affairs. In one of Plato's dialogues, Socrates notes: "Justice consists in everyone having their own and doing their own", "... minding your own business and not interfering with others - this is justice".

Justice preserves diversity in the world and is a guarantee that everything has its boundaries and its certainty. In a just society, therefore, the fate is different for the lazy and the hard worker, the criminal and the hero. But who determines fate? Isn't fate a matter of chance? Who among us can guarantee that our natural data, character traits, and habits constitute our choice?

A guarantee that our entire life and even our personal properties belong to us, characterize us, and are not derived from circumstances beyond our control, is equality of opportunity. The principle of equality is filled with existential meaning; it marks the refusal of society to decide for an individual those questions, the answers to which are related to value choice. The assimilation of values is a person's prerogative; society should be concerned with their coordination and the creation of a mechanism for their implementation. Ensuring equality is the elimination of the arbitrariness of human will in the lives of other people. In other words, the implementation of justice involves the destruction of the subjective will of those whose actions determine the fate of another person. If, say, I sell a product, then paying for it does not demonstrate to me the individual will of the

buyer, because every buyer is obliged to do the same when purchasing. Justice hides a template, a standard solution, thanks to which I have the opportunity to consider the results of interaction with other people as my merit or my defeat. This circumstance explains the internal need for justice in law, which determines certain patterns, and models of relationships, regardless of the characteristics of the individual will of persons entering into legal relations with each other. The rule of law has no address, it is abstract, and the rule of behavior formulated in it does not lose legal force depending on the subjective meaning of the life situation in which the bearers of mutual rights and obligations meet.

In a justly organized society, a person is returned the efforts he expended in the form of some benefits. Failure to replenish vital energy changes the guidelines of human activity, therefore society is objectively interested in ensuring that the lack of justice does not negatively affect the social activity of its members. Social injustice, elevated to a principle of state policy, makes it difficult for people to communicate, because it becomes unpredictable in its results. Work and creativity become meaningless, because success can become the cause of misfortune. With the reign of injustice, chance becomes the only law of social life, and the most effective form of protecting one's interests is violence. Injustice encroaches on existence, since the existence of something is possible only within the framework of the whole. It is in the nature of things that they correspond to each other; a violation of this correspondence changes the nature and results of their interaction: from constructive it turns into destructive. Refusal of proportionality in the natural and physical world is punishable: violation of proportions in the manufacture of medicine leads to the death of the patient, and violation of the ecological balance is fraught with the impoverishment of flora and fauna.

In the social world, injustice serves as a source of hostility between the individual and society. If injustice results in a loss of living space for a person, he does not consider himself bound by any obligations to him and is therefore ready to revolt. If injustice turns into undeserved success for a person, his fate is also

unenviable: he does not know the price of success and is doomed to defeat in a changed situation. The court poet will be consigned to oblivion, and the political leader, surrounded by flatterers, will be desecrated. Society, like an individual, loses its viability if the acquisition of goods is disproportionate to the efforts expended.

Thus, the necessary prerequisites for justice include the possibility of self-determination (freedom), equality, a mechanism for establishing social standards (law), a mechanism for the distribution of social benefits, and, finally, a value system, which in our case performs a symbolic function.

Since law is part of the content of justice, we need to understand the logic of those who contrast one thing to another. In particular, the position of contemporaries in relation to the law of past historical eras, as well as current ideological debates about which system of law is fairer, is of interest.

It seems that law cannot be assessed outside the value system that it serves. For the South, to define feudal law as “non-law,” one must not be a feudal lord, or at least not be in an interdependent relationship with him. The source of the moral pathos of modern denouncers of medieval orders is the rejection of the medieval person himself: he should be different (implied - like the author himself, who belongs to modern culture). Blood feuds or ordeals today outrage public legal consciousness, for which reason entire historical eras are declared illegal and deprived of rights. Trying to give law greater value, supporters of historical criticism of law only prove the opposite: without law one can live an entire era; law is an optional element of human culture.

Another educational situation is represented by the discussion about what kind of law we need. If law is a measure of justice achieved by society, it is clear that the measure is changeable. Sanctions of legal norms are flexible, the status of those convicted of a crime may vary in terms of the scope of legal restrictions etc.

Most of the critical statements about the injustice of law have nothing to do with the problem of justice since the object of one’s aspirations can only be

someone else's good. Since justice includes the possibility of self-determination, no one has sufficient grounds for making claims about his own worth to others. To impose one's being on another means to deprive that other of the freedom of self-determination. Therefore, for example, the request for reinstatement contains the personal interest of the dismissed employee. His demands for respect for labor rights are fair only in the aspect where he does not see only his own misfortune in this conflict.

The real confrontation between law and justice arises in the process of alienation from law. If justice goes beyond the boundaries of legal life, then this right becomes "alien." Behind this feeling are hidden expectations of a new law, where justice could be realized to the greatest extent. Therefore, the opposition between law and justice is in fact characteristic of a distrustful attitude towards law and power: their imperfection is unforgivable.

Law simplifies the view of a person, and therefore following the logic of justice is fraught with derogation of the principle of humanism. Justice strives for certainty; it forces the right to equate the actor with his action. Humanism denies this identity and does not recognize norms. From the point of view of justice, noted N.A. Berdyaev, a person is good because he acts well. In fact, the opposite is true: he acts well because he himself is good. It should be recognized that justice and humanism are two competing principles of law. One limits the action of the other. Law without justice is arbitrariness, and law without humanism is soulless logic that destroys humanity in the social. However, law cannot be higher than justice, and humanism is higher than law and justice, and its establishment in life does not have these values as its obligatory prerequisite.

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